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**THE IMPACT OF VOCATIONAL AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION ON THE ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT OF KANO STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The main Purpose of this study was to determine the impact of vocational and technical education on the economic development of Kano State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Two research questions were raised to guide the study; two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was one hundred and forty-four (144) people consisting of ninety-three (93) teachers and one hundred and fifty-one (151) VTE graduates of Technical Colleges. The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire which was validated by two experts. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question and Z-test was used to test the null hypotheses. This study found out that VTE programs in Kano state are not available enough to accommodate and train those that need and those that want it. The study also discovered that the contents of the available VTE programs in Kano state are only slightly relevant to the demand of labour market. The study recommends that the federal government and Kano state government should jointly establish more technical colleges in Kano state (especially in rural areas) to accommodate, train and produce more skilled human capital that can be employed by industries and SMEs or establish their own enterprise thereby contributing the economic development. The study also recommends that the available VTE programs should be updated to meet the job market demand. Collaboration and link should be established between technical colleges and industries to have synergy among themselves. Kano state government should also come up with internship programs for VTE graduates to prepare them for job market.

Keywords: Vocational Education, Technical Education, Economic Development

INTRODUCTION

The economic development and technological advancement of any society is determined by the number of skilled and educated human capital in that society. Thus, human capital is an essential determinant and a prime mover for the socio-economic development, technological advancement and standard of living. Human capital entails many factors such as education, health, technical and vocational training, and skill development. This implies that Economic development and technological advancement of any society cannot be attained without enhancing the general status of vocational training and competency, both formal and informal, embodied in its workforce or manpower. Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) plays a pivotal role in fostering economic development by equipping individuals with the necessary skills and competencies to thrive in the labour market. In the context of Kano State, Nigeria, VTE holds significant promise in addressing unemployment, enhancing productivity, and stimulating overall economic growth. One key driver of economic growth is a skilled workforce equipped with the necessary knowledge and practical abilities to contribute meaningfully to various sectors.

Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with these essential skills, thus making it a critical component of any nation's development strategy.

The demand for VTE is increasing as the world is moving towards industrialization and modernization, as the global manufacturing or industrial sectors contribute significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of all the developed and developing countries. The importance of and demand for VTE as a change agent for social, economic and technological development has been a subject of discussion in summits, academic conferences and policy circles in Nigeria and many other countries. In all the discussion, according to Ladipo (2017), there is a consensus that VTE is a secret behind the technological advancement and economic fortune of all the developed and developing countries in the world. Vocational and technical education is an indispensable instrument for improving labour mobility, adaptability and productivity. According to Mustafa (2015) VTE can help individuals to generate income and contribute significantly to the economic, social and even political development of their societies. He maintained that trained manpower through VTE is considered an important factor for the economic development of any society. According to ILO (2022), the most effective use of public resources is to improve the efficiency, competency and productivity of a workforce. Development of occupational skills through VTE leads to technological advancement that ensures optimum and efficient utilisation of resources and enhance productivity. VTE improves skills of work, economic development and helps in reducing unemployment, and enhance quality and efficiency of production. Better VTE, both formal and informal can refine the skills of required workforce which leads to a higher income and rapid economic development, resulting in better living standard. It enables workers to earn for themselves and create self-efficacy and satisfaction. It can reduce gender bias reduce unemployment, migration and dependency ratio. It prepares its graduates to a competitive workforce making it easy for them to find a better job or even engaged in their own enterprise. Investment in VTE becomes necessary for productivity, technological advancement, unemployment reduction and general economic development.

The economic prominence of Kano State dates back to precolonial time, flourishing as a center for trans-sahara trade. The city's famous "Kurmi Market" served as the crucial exchange point for goods (like kola nut, textiles, salt etc) and services (like weaving, blacksmithing and so on). During the British rule, the economy of Kano shifted to groundnut production, becoming the major exporter of the crop. This led to the development of groundnut and other crops processing industries and infrastructures, further solidifying the economy of the state. Kano is currently a significant industrial center with sectors like food processing, textile, leather work, and many other sectors. These service and production sectors play a vital role in the economic development of the state.

The link between the availability of vocational and technological education programs and economic development has been a subject of much research and discussion over the years. This is particularly relevant in the context of developing countries like Nigeria, where economic growth and diversification are crucial national goals. The types and availability of VTE programs have evolved over the years to meet the changing needs of industries and businesses. According to Brown et al. (2017), there has been a shift towards more specialized and industry-specific programs in fields such as information technology, healthcare, and advanced manufacturing. Additionally, there has been an emphasis on partnerships between educational institutions, industries and businesses, to ensure that VTE programs are aligned with industry standards and workforce demands.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

While various initiatives exist in Kano state to promote VTE, there is a need to assess the availability and comprehensiveness of these skill acquisition programs in Kano. It is essential to determine how well these programs align with the state's economic needs, particularly in catering for diverse industries and emerging sectors. A thorough evaluation of the scope and diversity of VTE programs will provide insights into their adequacy in addressing labour market demands.

A major concern is the relevance of VTE programs to the actual requirements of employers. The persistent gap between the skills taught in technical colleges and those required in the workforce raises questions about the employability of VTE graduates. If the existing programs do not adequately prepare graduates for the labour market, they may contribute to unemployment rather than alleviate it. Therefore, it is necessary to examine whether VTE graduates possess the skills and competencies that align with industry expectations.

Additionally, while VTE programs continue to produce graduates, there is little clarity on the extent of availability and skill levels of these individuals in Kano's labour market. The lack of reliable data makes it difficult for employers to source qualified personnel and for policymakers to identify areas that require increased graduate output. Understanding the extent to which VTE programs supply skilled manpower is crucial for assessing their impact on workforce development.

In a nutshell, while VTE is recognized as a key driver of economic development that equips individuals with practical skills that enhance employability and efficiency in place of work, Kano state still faces the challenge of unemployment among youth population due to bad condition of VTE. This results in many social vices such as phone snatch, street rubbery, political thuggery and so on, which have a negative on the economic development of the state. This study therefore seeks to find out the solution to above stated problem in the state.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to determine the impact of vocational and technical education on the economic development of Kano State. Specifically, the study proposes to determine the;

- i. VTE programs available in Kano State Technical Colleges.
- ii. relevance of the available VTE programs in Kano to the demand of labour market.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions will be answered by f the study.

- i. What are the availale VTE programs in Kano State Technical Colleges?
- ii. How relevant are the VTE programs in Kano to the needs of labour market?

HYPOTHESES

The following four null hypotheses (H_0) were guided the study and they were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- i. **H₀₁**:- There is no significant difference between the mean responses of the teachers and VTE graduates on the availability of VTE programs in Kano State Technical Colleges.
- ii. **H₀₂**:- There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and VTE graduates on the relevance of the contents of VTE programs to the demand of labour market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on Human Capital Theory founded by Adam Smith in 1960s, which states that investment in education is necessary to acquire skills and training which, in turn, will increase individual capital. Human Capital Theory (HCT) is directly related to this study because it emphasizes the role of education and skills in enhancing productivity and economic growth.

Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory is a framework that conceptualizes individuals' skills, knowledge, and capabilities as valuable assets contributing to economic productivity and growth. It is originated in the works of economists like Gary Becker in the 1960s and has since become a central concept in understanding the role of education and training in economic development. Human capital is the stock of knowledge, skills, abilities, and other attributes embodied in individuals that contribute to their economic productivity and earning potential. Over the past decade, the importance of human capital in driving economic development has been increasingly recognized by scholars and policymakers in many countries.

Research from the World Bank (World Bank, 2018) highlights those investments in human capital, such as education and healthcare, are essential for promoting economic growth, reducing poverty, and increasing societal well-being. Furthermore, studies have shown that improvements in human capital can lead to higher labour productivity, innovation, and technological advancement (Barro, 2015).

Availability of VTE Programs

Availability of VTE programs cater to evolving workforce demands and drives economic growth. According to CEDEFOP (2021), availability of diverse and broad array of VTE programs effectively bridges skill gaps across various industries. By aligning training with labour market needs, availability of diverse VTE programs can cultivate a skilled workforce equipped to meet employer demands, propelling economic progress. Lee (2019) also opined that availability VTE programs that prioritize skill development in a diverse emerging sector, such as renewable energy or artificial intelligence, and so on, can become catalysts for innovation. Availability of well-diversed workforce in cutting-edge technologies stimulates economic competitiveness and growth. A report by World Bank (2020) highlighted those countries with robust and diverse VTE systems attract foreign direct investment (FDI) due to the availability of skilled labor. Increased FDI inflows contribute to infrastructure development, job creation, and technology transfer, bolstering the broader economy.

Relevance of VTE Programs to the Demand of Labour Market

Labour Market according to Ehrenberg & Smith (2022) is where knowledge, skills, abilities and human work experiences are presented in exchange for wages and the meeting of other work-related goals such as socialization, learning, career and economic advancement, life balance, social relevance and so forth. In this sense, the labour market offers more than jobs and wages but serves important ends for employers, employees, government and society. Additionally, the labour market exists to give room for individuals to express their potential through useful activities that are aimed at meeting the need to produce, offer service and earn wages. the primary thrust for the existence of a labour market is that man exists within a community of others, called society. According to European Commission (2023), labour market is the mechanism through which supply (workers seeking employment) and demand (employers seeking workers) for labour interact to determine wages, employment levels, and working conditions.

Knowledge, skill and abilities (KSAs) possessed by an individual become significant if they are relevant and applicable in the specific organization they elect to work for. The KSA should, to a high extent, provide extensive opportunity for the individual who possesses it to have a high probability of securing employment. However, world has reported many graduates completing their college studies but missing the necessary skills to meet the labour market requirements (Suarta, 2017). Researches revealed that most students were found to possess academic certificates with good grade classification but only to find that they cannot be employed in the current labour market (Salas, 2017). Wang and Li (2017) revealed that the significant source of these discrepancies is the nature of education and the pieces of training they are provided being not focused on labour market requirements on demand.

Concept of Economic Development

Economic Development is a complex and multifaceted concept that goes beyond simply increasing the size of an economy (Minini & Deebari, 2023). There is no clear picture or definition of what actually constitutes “economic underdevelopment” or how to achieve it, as it is an evolving concept, and keeps altering over time. The concept of "economic development" has undergone a significant transformation over the years. It has shifted from a purely GDP-centric focus towards a more multifaceted concepts and perspectives, encompassing societal well-being, environmental sustainability, inclusive growth and many other dimensions.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study was a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was four hundred and forty-eight (448) people consisting of ninety-three (93) teachers and one hundred and fifty-one (151) VTE graduates of Technical Colleges and two hundred selected (200) SMEs owners in Kano state. A sample of 100 VTE graduates and 73 teachers of Technical Colleges (Secondary School) within Kano state were randomly selected from the total target population using "stratified sampling technique", where the target population was divided into strata or subgroups, that is (VTE teachers and graduates) and then the sample was randomly selected from each stratum. The instrument for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire called Impact of Vocational and Technical Education on Economic Development of Kano State. The questionnaire was drafted based on the specific purposes/objectives of the study and the research questions. In order to confirm the validity of the instrument for the study, the instrument was subjected to face validation by two lecturers in the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adamawa University (MAU) Yola. To guarantee the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was carried out in Gombe State, Nigeria. The instrument was administered to the teachers, and data obtained was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha method to determine the reliability coefficient range, and value obtained was 8.84 which is within the accepted range. The data collected from the target population was analysed using mean and standard deviation in answering the research questions. Z-test was also used, because of the large population under the study, in testing the four null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any item with a mean value of 4.00 was accepted as highly available, highly relevant or highly employed. Any item with a mean value of 3.00-3.90 was accepted as moderately available, moderately relevant or moderate employed. Any item with a mean value of 2.00-2.90 is accepted as slightly available, slightly relevant.

RESULTS

Research Question One: How available are VTE programs in Kano State?

Table 1: Means responses of Teachers on the availability of VTE programs in Kano

SN	Program	Teachers		VTE Graduates		Items Grand		Remark
		1	σ_1	2	σ_2	G	σ_G	
1	Auto-Mechanic	2.48	0.70	2.11	0.63	2.27	0.66	Slightly Available
2	Blocklaying, Bricklaying and Concreting	2.36	0.96	2.06	0.66	2.19	0.81	Slightly Available
3	Carpentry & Joinery	2.40	0.621	2.24	0.75	2.30	0.69	Slightly Available
4	Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work	2.45	0.53	2.27	0.74	2.34	0.66	Slightly Available
5	Plumbing and Pipe Fitting	2.15	0.92	1.76	0.75	2.17	0.83	Slightly Available
6	Radion and Television	2.23	0.72	2.18	0.68	2.21	0.70	Slightly Available
7	Refrigeration and air conditioning	1.63	0.84	1.78	0.72	1.72	0.77	Not Available
8	Welding and Fabrication	2.58	0.76	1.19	0.79	1.77	0.78	Not Available
Cumulative Grand Mean						2.11		Slightly Available

μ_1 = Mean Response of Teachers, μ_2 = Mean Response of VTE Graduates, σ_1 = Standard Deviation for Teachers' Response, σ_2 = Standard Deviation for VTE Graduates' Response, G = Grand Mean and σ_G = Grand Standard Deviation.

Table 1 shows the mean responses and standard deviation of teachers and VTE graduates on the availability of VTE programs in Kano state. The table revealed that six items have a grand mean value ranging from 2.17 to 2.34 which are within 2 points indicating that these were agreed by the respondents to be slightly available (SA). Two items (items 7 and 8) has a mean value of 1.77 and 1.78 which means that it was agreed by the respondents to be not available in Kano state. The grand standard deviation of all the eight items ranges from 0.53 to 0.96. The values are low, which means the respondents were close in their responses. With a cumulative grand mean of 2.11 it implies that VTE programs in Kano state are slightly available.

Research Question 2: How relevant are the content of the available VTE programs in Kano to the demand of labour market?

Table 2: Mean responses of Teachers and VTE graduates on the relevance of the contents of VTE programs in Kano state labour market.

SN	Items (Programs)	Teachers		VTE Graduates		Items Grand		Remark
		μ_1	σ_1	μ_2	σ_2	μ_g	σ_g	
1	Ato-Mechanic	2.48	0.60	2.57	0.65	2.53	0.63	Slightly Relevant
2	Blocklaying, Bricklaying and Concreting	1.60	1.03	2.53	0.69	2.13	0.66	Slightly Relevant
3	Carpentry & Joinery	2.50	0.70	2.54	0.71	2.53	0.71	Slightly Relevant
4	Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work	1.89	0.71	2.52	0.70	2.25	0.74	Slightly Relevant
5	Plumbing and Pipe Fitting	2.70	0.73	2.13	0.80	2.37	0.77	Slightly Relevant
6	Radion and Television	1.84	0.92	2.24	0.78	2.07	0.84	Slightly Relevant
7	Refrigeration and air conditioning	2.22	0.65	2.04	0.69	2.12	0.67	Slightly Relevant
8	Welding and Fabrication	2.86	0.67	2.59	1.09	2.70	0.83	Slightly Relevant
Cumulative Grand Mean						2.34		Slightly Relevant

μ_1 = Mean Response of Teachers, μ_2 = Mean Response of VTE Graduates, σ_1 = Standard Deviation for Teachers' Response, σ_2 = Standard Deviation for VTE Graduates' Response, μ_g = Grand Mean and σ_g = Grand Standard Deviation.

Table 2 above shows the mean responses and standard deviations of Teachers and VTE graduates on the relevance of the contents of VTE programs to the demand of labour market. The table revealed that all the eight items have a grand mean value ranging from 2.07 to 2.70 which indicates that the contents of all the programs were agreed by the respondent that they are slightly relevant to the demand of labour market. The grand standard deviation of all the eight items ranges from 0.63 to 0.83. Each value is low, which means the respondents were close in their responses. With a cumulative grand mean of 2.34 it implies that contents of VTE programs in Kano state are slightly relevant to the demand of labour market.

H₀₁:- There is no significant difference between the mean responses of the teachers and VTE graduates on the availability of VTE programs in Kano State Technical Colleges.

Table 3: Summary of the Result of Z-Test for the Significant Difference Between The Mean Responses of Teachers And VTE Graduates on the Availability of VTE Programs In Kano Sate.

Hypothesis	Z-Calculated	P-Value	Level of Significance	Remark
H ₀₁	3.91	1.96	0.05	Significant

Table 3 above shows Z-Test statistical result of mean difference between the responses of teachers and VTE graduates on the availability of VTE programs in Kano state. The result shows that Z-calculated is 3.91 and P-value is 1.96, that is Z-calculated is greater than P-value ($Z > P$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, meaning that there is significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and VTE graduates on the availability of VTE programs in Kano state.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and VTE graduates on the relevance of the contents of VTE programs to the demand of labour market

Table 4: Summary of the Result of Z-Test for the Significant Difference Between the Mean Responses of Teachers and VTE Graduates on the Relevance of The Contents of VTE Programs to the Demand Of Labour Market

Hypothesis	Z-Calculated	P-Value	Level of Significance	Not Significant
H ₀₂	0.09	1.96	0.05	Not Significant

Table 4 above shows Z-Test statistical result of difference between the mean responses of teachers and VTE graduates on the relevant of the content of VTE programs to the demand of labour market. The result shows that Z-calculated is 0.09 and P-value is 1.96, that is Z-calculated is less that P-value ($Z < P$). The null hypothesis is there accepted failed reject), meaning that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and VTE graduates on the relevance of the content of VTE programs to the demand of labour market.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Finding of the research question one revealed that VTE programs in Kano state are only slightly available as indicated by the cumulative grand mean below 2.5. This suggest that VTE programs are not available enough in Kano state to accommodate those that want it, an outcome that is line with Adeyemi and Ojo (2022) who reported that VTE are not available enough in Nigeria. This affirms that VTE programs are not available enough to accommodate those that want it and those that want it. However, Adeyemi and Adeyanju (2021) found that there is a variety of VTE programs in Lagos state. Okolocha and Egbunne (2019) also found that there are many VTE programs in Delta state. Furthermore, Akinsolu and Adeniram found that there are diverse VTE programs. Collectively, these findings contradict the current study, meaning that there are VTE programs available in some parts of Nigeria.

Findings of research question two revealed that the contents of the VTE programs in Kano state are slightly relevant to the demand of labour market as indicated by the cumulative grand mean of 2.35. This indicates that contents of the VTE programs are not closely relevant to the employers' demand, aligning with Okolocha and Egbunne (2019) who discovered

that VTE programs in Delta state not are closely relevant to the demand of labour market. Furthermore, Adeyemi and Alabi (2021) discovered that VTE programs in Nigeria lack relevance to SMEs demands. Ibrahim and Ahmed (2023) also found that there is a gap between the skills provided by VTE programs in Nigeria and labour market demand. Thus, the finding of this study affirms that VTE programs in technical colleges are not relevant to the demand of labour market.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, the study brought to light the factors that militate against the contribution of VTE to the economic development of Kano state, which include inadequacy of VTE programs (Technical Colleges), gap between skills taught in the technical colleges and the skills needed in the labour market, mismatch between the contents of the VTE and industry requirement which led to lack trained VTE graduates in labour market that can be employed and establish their own business. The study also highlighted some strategies that could be used to enhance the impact of VTE to the economic development of Kano state, which include establishing more technical colleges (especially in rural areas), establishing a link or connection between technical colleges and industries, updating the contents of VTE programs to the demand of labour market, establishing an internship program for VTE graduates.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. More Technical colleges should be established (especially in rural areas) so that the program would be available and accessible for those that need it and those want it and to produce more skilled human capital.
- ii. Link and Collaboration should be established between industries/SMEs Technical Colleges so that the VTE students will be trained based on the needs of the industries
- iii. VTE curriculum should be revised to suit the current need of industries.
- iv. Internship program for VTE graduates should be established to enhance their skills and make them more employable or more able establish their own enterprise.

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